

S-BVT for next-generation optical metro networks: benefits, design and key enabling technologies

Michela Svaluto Moreolo*, Josep M. Fabrega, Laia Nadal

Centre Tecnologic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC), Av. Carl Friedrich Gauss 7, 08860 Castelldefels (Barcelona), Spain.

ABSTRACT

This work elaborates on: i) why the sliceable bandwidth variable transceiver (S-BVT) represents a key enabler for next-generation optical metro networks; ii) how it should be designed to take benefit of its capabilities and advanced features; and iii) which are the promising technologies to be adopted addressing the most relevant requirements and challenges. Specifically, S-BVT architectures based on multicarrier modulation and flexi-grid technologies, adopting cost-effective optoelectronic front-ends, enable flexible adaptation to dynamic traffic and variable path condition, targeting high capacity and scalability, while saving network resources and costs. Programmability and modularity are envisioned for integration in software-defined optical metro networks.

Keywords: sliceable bandwidth variable transceiver (S-BVT), multicarrier modulation, OFDM, programmable transceivers, flexi-grid technologies, adaptive software-defined optical transmission, software defined networking, next-generation optical metro networks.

1. INTRODUCTION

Driven by novel and bandwidth-hungry services, and the need for heterogeneous and data-intensive traffic aggregation/delivery, a migration towards a more dynamic, efficient and agile paradigm is envisioned for optical metropolitan area networks (MANs). To address the challenges and requirements of this scenario, the sliceable bandwidth/bitrate variable transceiver appears an attractive solution, when suitably tailored for this network segment¹⁻⁴.

A bandwidth/bitrate variable transceiver (BVT) is a transceiver able to vary its capacity by suitably adapting the occupied bandwidth and the supported bitrate; the frequency slots as well as the carrier wavelength can be selected according to the flexi-grid paradigm, in order to make an optimal usage of the available spectral resources². A sliceable BVT (S-BVT) can be seen as a set of virtual transceivers, transmitting multiple flows of variable capacity each⁵. It is also capable of transmitting an aggregated flow of variable capacity. Thus, the S-BVT is able to concurrently serve multiple endpoints or either the same destination node via multiple paths. Each BVT as well as the S-BVT can be programmed to support the remote control and configuration of their elements, parameters, functions and operation modes.

The integration of BVTs and S-BVTs in a software defined network (SDN) enables the on-demand configuration of programmable network functions, such as rate, bandwidth, path adaptation, and slice-ability. As additional benefit deriving from the (S)-BVT flexibility, a vast range of granularities can be handled, from the sub-wavelength to the super-wavelength level¹⁻². These features and capabilities are particularly relevant for the dynamic requirements and flexibility challenges of future optical metro networks.

This work contributes to elaborate on three main questions about the use of S-BVT in next-generation optical metro networks: i) why the S-BVT represents a key enabler; ii) how it should be designed to take benefits of its capabilities and advanced features and iii) which are the most relevant requirements to be satisfied, the limitations to be addressed/overcome and the promising technologies to be adopted.

Particularly, cost-optimized modular architecture designs enable multi-adaptive software-defined optical transmission. The transmission technology choice is fundamental for the S-BVT architecture design, envisioning a migration towards a more flexible paradigm and targeting SDN-enabled advanced functionalities.

*michela.svaluto@cttc.es; phone +34 93 645 29 00; fax: +34 93 645 29 01; www.cttc.es

The adoption of multicarrier modulation (MCM) and flexi-grid technologies for on-demand spectral manipulation with fine granularity is envisioned to be combined with cost-effective optoelectronic front-ends.

Furthermore, multiple dimensions exploiting band multiplexing and/or polarization multiplexing can be adopted, with a limited number of building blocks, enhancing the S-BVT capacity and spectral efficiency to support traffic from/to multiple tenants in highly flexible/scalable software-defined optical metro networks.

The use of S-BVT with advanced monitoring capabilities enables efficient SDN programming and resources saving, coping with the cost/energy requirements of optical metro networks. This together with the adoption of suitable photonic technologies, limiting the complexity and cost of the implementation, will draw the way towards cost-efficient, dynamic and software-defined optical metro networks.

2. S-BVT AS A KEY ENABLER

In this section, we elaborate on the S-BVT as a key enabler for next-generation optical metro networks, particularly focusing on addressing the question on why adopting this data plane element for this network segment.

On one side, a convergence of aggregation and metro networks towards the access segment is envisioned to support the novel bandwidth-hungry services and users demand. On the other side, an evolutionary network scenario requires to provide suitable IP/cloud connectivity at the network nodes, including the centralization of IP edge functionalities in virtual server farms hosted in distributed data centers.

Actually, since main network operators have been recently expanding their photonic mesh to the regional networks, it has been proposed to extend the aggregation network reach, typically confined in a metropolitan area⁴. This is mainly driven by the need of virtualizing the network functions/functionalities to allow significant reductions in Capital Expenditure (CapEx) investment. In a scenario, where these functionalities are virtualized, a flexi-grid regional photonic mesh network could conveniently provide connections between several tenants/users and the different data centers, by following the SDN principles and exploiting the advanced features of new transmission technologies such as flexi-grid transponders. Particularly, the S-BVT capability of slicing the transmission to concurrently serve multiple destinations through the individual control of its carriers is well suited for the point-to-multipoint communication required for this use case. Thus, the advanced functionalities and technologies adopted in the core networks, if appropriately tailored, can be advantageously used in the MAN, blurring the boundary between the two segments.

Particularly, the transceiver modularity as well as the S-BVT architecture design is crucial to address the stringent cost target of the metro network segment. The S-BVT architecture allows to be easily upgraded according to the network needs. Additionally, alternative solutions have been proposed for a cost-effective S-BVT design.

Furthermore, the programmability of the S-BVT has a key role towards the integration of the data and control planes to support advanced functionalities in flexible/elastic and highly scalable software defined optical metro networks.

Finally, the advanced (S)-BVT features can be also complemented by the design and development of specific cost-sensitive monitoring techniques, capable to estimate different quality of service (QoS) parameters and deliver them to the suitable control plane entities.

2.1 Modularity

Modularity is a very important feature for easily upgrading the transceiver architecture, by simply including/integrating additional modules, according to the network evolution and requirements. A modular architecture allows improving the system scalability, e.g. following a pay-as-you-grow model.

Figure 1 shows a schematic of a generic S-BVT with a modular architecture: the transceiver is composed of an array of N BVT modules, each of them can be designed and adapted to have variable capacity. The multiple flows are optically aggregated/distributed by using a bandwidth variable (BV) wavelength selective switch (WSS), or spectral selective switch (SSS), with N ports, that can be implemented in liquid crystal on silicon (LCoS) technology. In order to facilitate the slicing, selection and routing of the multiple flow(s), also the metro network nodes can be equipped with BV-WSS. Nevertheless, the flexibility of a fixed grid optical metro network can be improved by simply doting the S-BVT with this programmable variable switching element².

Figure 1. Optical metro network scenario, adopting BVTs and S-BVTs able to aggregate a variable number of flows (N). The schematic of an S-BVT with modular architecture is detailed. In the inset, the transmitter (Tx) and receiver (Rx) main building blocks of a BVT module are indicated.

Additionally, since the different transceivers modules composing the S-BVT are expected to have similar architecture, they can be embedded in a single substrate, adopting photonic integrated circuit (PIC) technology, for a significant reduction in terms of cost and power consumption.

Indeed, in an evolutionary metro/regional network scenario, the advanced features of new transmission technologies, the introduction of flexi-grid data plane elements and the modularity of the transceiver architecture can be advantageously/suitably exploited to enable a smooth network upgrading and favor a soft migration towards a flexible grid paradigm.

2.2 Programmability and advanced features

Data plane elements, and particularly the S-BVT, can be designed to be adaptive and programmable by means of specific agents enabling their (re)-configuration. The SDN controller is responsible for the programming of the S-BVTs and the data plane elements via their agents. The agents map the high-level operations coming from the SDN controller into low-level, hardware-dependent operations.

As shown in Figure 2, the SDN controller is also responsible for the provisioning of the metro network optical channels, for example by means of an active stateful path computation element (PCE). Thus, the SDN controller coordinates the optical path(s) establishment, the channel state information (CSI) estimation and triggering, the monitoring of specific parameters related to the signal quality and the S-BVT configuration for a successful transmission.

The programmable data plane elements of the S-BVT are the BVT modules and the BV-WSS. Within each BVT module, the DSP block allows to select/adapt variable parameters, such as the subcarrier, the modulation format and power per each subcarrier, the occupied frequency slots, the data rate, and the number of flows. In addition, it is possible to activate the transmission of probing signals in order to retrieve the CSI. Accordingly, the subcarrier loading is adapted to achieve the successful data flow transmission at a target bitrate over the established path (target reach). Furthermore, the DSP at the receiver enables channel equalization, signal monitoring and performance evaluation, according to the target performance. The capability of electrical/optical performance monitoring per S-BVT subcarrier could be achieved by means of a synergic interworking among data plane elements (transceivers and optical nodes), control plane and advanced acquisition techniques^{6,7}; further details on this aspect are provided in section 2.3. The digital block also enables to adopt a specific forward error correction (FEC), e.g. hard- or soft-decision FEC, and the related overhead³. In addition to the adaptability at the DSP, also the sampling rate of digital-to-analog converter (DAC) and analog-to-digital converter (ADC) can be programmed according to the transmitted flow.

The programmable elements at the optoelectronic front-end of the BVT module include the tunable laser source (TLS) for enabling/disabling the transmission of each flow and the corresponding wavelength and power setting. Also the photodetectors at the receiver can be enabled/disabled, accordingly. Another programmable element is the external modulator: for example, the bias of a Mach-Zehnder modulator (MZM) can be automatically controlled⁸. The filtering stages included in the S-BVT architecture are tunable to allow selecting the suitable filter bandwidth and appropriate central wavelength.

Figure 2. SDN-enabled S-BVT including monitoring capability for software defined optical metro network. In the inset, the main programmable elements at the Tx and Rx of the single BVT module are detailed for software defined data flow transmission at a target Rx performance over the established path (target reach), after CSI estimation with probe signal.

Finally, another key programmable element is the BV-WSS, at the S-BVT and at the network nodes of a flexible metro network. The BV-WSS ports are enabled/disabled according to the number of active BVT modules; the bandwidth, wavelength and attenuation of the active ports are remotely configured by the SDN-controller for properly aggregating, disaggregating and optically equalizing the data flows.

The S-BVT programmable elements enable multiple advanced features. First of all, the intrinsic slice-ability of the S-BVT, as a pool of virtual transceivers, allows transmitting high capacity flow as a superchannel or either opportunely splitting the traffic into multiple lower capacity flows. The multiple flows can be transmitted over independent paths to concurrently serve multiple endpoints of the network or the same end-node. This last is the case of inverse multiplexing, that is an advanced feature enabling to conveniently target specific network requirements, according to the channel state and spectrum occupation⁹. Thanks to the S-BVT adaptability feature, the bit and baud rate can be maximized over the established path to achieve a target performance, or alternatively, the performance can be maximized, suitably fixing the rate over the selected link, according to the traffic demand/request. All these features allow an efficient and dynamic usage of the network resources, and the mitigation of spectrum fragmentation. In addition, the S-BVT ability of grid adaptation enables a soft migration towards flexible technologies, even in fixed-grid optical metro networks. Particularly, it has been demonstrated that the use of an SDN-enabled S-BVT with a total capacity above 200Gb/s in a fixed-grid optical metro network (testbed with single-hop path up to 150km), a 50% spectral saving at the expense of 12% rate decrease, by fitting more than one flow within the same 100GHz ITU-T channel².

2.3 Monitoring

Optical performance monitoring of signal quality is a key enabler of intelligent optical networks, as it facilitates to suitably allocate and manage the network resource and to cope with signal degradation. The S-BVT is appropriately (re)-configured accordingly, for SDN and cognitive networking¹⁰. The monitoring parameters acquisition can be performed either in the optical domain at the network nodes or in the digital/electrical domain at the edge (destination) node (requiring optical-to-electrical conversion and signal demodulation). Some advanced modulation formats, such as MCM, provide the transmission system with self-performance monitoring ability. In this case, thanks to the transmitted overhead of information, a set of system parameters can be acquired in the electrical domain and related to the optical SNR (OSNR) of the signal⁷. This is performed at the DSP of the (S)-BVT receiver. However, when the adopted transceivers are pluggable modules, which is the current preferred option in the metro segment, integrated receivers can be seen as a black box, leading to uncertainty in the evaluation of the OSNR through the electrical SNR. A preliminary calibration step can be performed to take into account the not ideal response/transfer function of the optical/electrical components and thus prevent OSNR estimation errors⁷.

Subcarrier monitoring in the optical domain allows to dynamically reconfigure the parameters of each BVT of the S-BVT array, in order to overcome the degradation of specific subcarriers without any data reception/decoding.

We have demonstrated that it is possible to derive the CSI from the in-band measurements performed in the optical domain, in order to automatically configure the S-BVT⁷. Assuming to adopt an S-BVT with a very fine granularity, this

non-intrusive method requires a high-resolution optical spectrum analyzer (OSA) for suitably monitoring each subchannel (slices) of the aggregated multi-flow (see Figure 2).

Thus, a transparent signal quality monitoring per subcarrier can be performed at the edge nodes of the MAN, as well as at any node of the metro network equipped with a monitoring system. The monitoring module consists of a measurement equipment (OSA) with appropriate resolution and the related SDN agent. This enables the SDN controller to efficiently manage the acquired monitoring parameters, opportunely processed either locally or within a distributed/centralized data center.

Once acquired the live monitoring information, with the in-band knowledge of transmission impairments and signal degradation level, the control layer with the SDN controller can dynamically reconfigure the S-BVT parameters to cope with the signal degradation at specific subcarriers, activating the resiliency mechanism without the need for optical-to-electrical conversion and data demodulation. In addition to the S-BVT (re)-configuration, the monitoring at the network nodes enables the early detection of in-band signal degradation in order to efficiently manage the traffic add/drop, routing and/or grooming processes.

3. MODULAR S-BVT DESIGN

In this section, to answer the second question proposed in the introduction, we present some guidelines for the S-BVT design. Particularly we focus on the main blocks of the BVT module, as shown in Figure 3. Indeed, a key challenge to take into account is the cost-effectiveness target required by metro network applications.

Figure 3. BVT module design. DSP blocks based on MCM (DMT/OFDM), including adaptive mapper for CSI estimation and BL/PL; in the inset, example of BL assignment for a 20GHz bandwidth signal after 50km link¹¹. Alternative front-end schemes.

3.1 Multicarrier modulation

If the programmable BVT module of the S-BVT is based on MCM, such as discrete multitone (DMT) and orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM), it enables spectral manipulation at the subcarrier level.

Specifically, each subcarrier can be individually adjusted (with subwavelength granularity) to support arbitrary modulation format, in order to achieve the targeted rate/reach and bandwidth (frequency slots) occupancy. This is particularly attractive to maximize the capacity per flow and extend the achievable reach over uncompensated optical link in the MAN.

This is enabled by including in the DSP block of the BVT module, adaptive bit/power loading (BL/PL) algorithms, which can be optimal (Levin-Campello) or suboptimal (Chow-Cioffi-Bingham). Usually, the CSI is estimated by transmitting a probe signal with uniform loading (UL) and according to this information, the mapper adaptively loads each subcarrier with the suitable number of bit and power value. The algorithms can work in rate adaptive or margin adaptive mode depending on the network priority target^{2,11,12}.

The training symbols (TS) are used for equalization and self-performance monitoring. In order to simplify the DSP computational complexity, real-valued transform alternative to the fast Fourier transform (FFT), such as the fast Hartley

transform (FHT), can be adopted depending on the DMT or OFDM scheme implemented at the BVT module⁴, as shown in Figure 3.

3.2 Cost effective front-ends

In order to design the optoelectronic front-ends of an S-BVT for optical metro network, two strategies can be adopted: i) design simplified architectures at any node of the network or ii) adopt centralized more complex S-BVT shared among multiple users equipped with simplified (S)-BVT architecture. The former approach preferably considers direct detection (DD) transceivers^{2,12}, while the latter can combine simple DMT transmission at the tenants with shared coherent receiver (CO-Rx) at the centralized S-BVT as shown in Figure 3.

DMT is the simplest MCM technique; thus, it allows conveniently designing cost-effective transceivers for metro networks. The BVT module can therefore adopt optoelectronic front-end based on intensity modulation (IM), with direct or external modulation, and DD, including a simple PIN photodetector. Solutions based on direct modulated laser (DML) can be envisioned to lower the BVT module cost, carefully taking into account the trade-off in terms of performance due to chirping effect and limited range of tune-ability. DMT with amplitude modulation can be considered to extend the achievable reach when combined with more complex centralized S-BVT, for example based on intradyne reception featuring phase diversity⁴.

When external modulation is adopted in the S-BVT design, cost-effective options for the TLS can be considered, especially if there isn't a stringent constraint on the laser linewidth. The S-BVT can be also designed to have a single multi-wavelength source to drive the array of N modulators, each one belonging to a different BVT module. In this case, the trade-off consists on the limited tune-ability compared to the array of N TLS.

In order to mitigate the chromatic dispersion, which severely affects IM/DD systems, and thus further extend the achievable reach, covering the metro/regional network segment, vestigial side-band or single side-band (SSB) OFDM can be implemented, with or without guard interval (to fully exploit the available bandwidth)¹¹. In this case the external MZM modulator should be properly biased (for linear field modulation). The additional filtering stage required for SSB modulation can be supplied by the BV-WSS, serving as both flow aggregator and SSB optical filter.

3.3 Band multiplexing and polarization multiplexing

The S-BVT modules can support subcarrier multiplexing, also referred as multi-band OFDM (MB-OFDM). This alternative module design lowers the number of required optoelectronic blocks to serve multiple endpoints of the optical metro network: a single BVT module generating M bands can serve up to M tenants⁴.

The multi-band signal can be generated either in the optical domain or in the electrical domain. The former use optical mixing¹³, the latter approach requires radio frequency (RF) mixing^{4,14}.

Figure 4. Modular S-BVT architecture with subcarrier multiplexing (module- N) and PDM (module- n) capability. In the inset, multi-band BVTx option based on (a) digital RF mixing and (b) analog RF mixing.

Figure 4 illustrates two alternative schemes (a and b, in the inset) to perform the RF up-conversion at the multi-band transmitter. The digital scheme allows to perform a software-defined band tuning over the spectrum. The system flexibility is enhanced without any additional electronic hardware, but requires a single higher speed DAC. The electrical mixing is hardware-based, and cannot be arbitrarily tuned, but relaxes the requirements on DAC/ADC. When design an (S)-BVT, this trade-off should be taken into account in order to meet the requirements of the targeted metro network application/use case.

The S-BVT modules can be also designed to support polarization division multiplexing (PDM). The PDM BVT module uses a single laser source and the design includes polarization controllers and beam splitters/combiners. This feature allows exploiting the polarization as additional S-BVT dimension, increasing the flexibility and efficiency in terms of system and network resources. In fact, different data flows can be assigned to different polarization components. According to the channel condition and network requirements, they can be enabled/disabled and transmitted along different optical paths. Furthermore, if the nodes of the optical metro network are equipped with the suitable components (available on-demand), the PDM capability can be also exploited to flexibly distribute the slices towards different receiver locations. A cost-efficient programmable S-BVT with PDM capability and flexible distributed DD has been demonstrated³.

4. KEY ISSUES AND CONCLUDING REMARKS

The most relevant key issues related to next generation optical metro networks are posed by the high bandwidth pressure and the traffic dynamicity, to support novel services and the ever increasing traffic demand, while keeping low the CapEx and operational expenditure (OpEx). In the following, we aim at answering the last main question proposed in this work. The challenges consist of enhancing the network scalability, granularity and spectral/resource efficiency, while increasing the system capacity and extending the achievable reach, by adopting cost-effective solutions.

The S-BVT architecture and design alternatives presented in Sections 2 and 3 provide promising solutions to address these challenges and meet the metro segment requirements. Indeed, a modular S-BVT can be upgraded, adding BVT modules, providing increased scalability.

An intelligent management of the optical metro network for an optimal usage of the network resources is possible by introducing SDN and flexi-grid technologies in MAN. The adoption of S-BVT with the SDN-control of its data plane elements enables the integration of novel advanced abilities in optical metro networks, as evidenced by the experimental results obtained for an S-BVT with a total capacity above 200Gb/s².

Thanks to its multiple advanced functionalities, an SDN-enabled S-BVT allows remotely programming and dynamically (re)configuring specific parameters/characteristics, according to the metro network priority (e.g. high-capacity, long-distance and low power consumption) to meet the traffic demand, channel bandwidth/path/state and energy efficiency requirements. This is of particular interest for addressing the intrinsic dynamicity and uncertainty of traffic pattern, the ever increasing capacity demand and the wide range of signals with different levels of granularity to be supported in next-generation metro networks. The maximization of capacity/distance and minimization of power consumption as priority targets can be achieved by adding a policy-based control in the S-BVT, as demonstrated for a programmable cost-effective 400-G transceiver¹².

Improving the programmability of the data plane and its integration with the control plane represents an added value to the network. Nevertheless, this implies a huge amount of information, that the SDN-controller should collect and process. The increase of the complexity of programmable elements and parameters to be managed could affect the network efficiency in terms of cost and latency, which represent another key requirement for the metro segment. Thus, these issues should be carefully considered for a correct dimensioning, modelling and design of the programmable S-BVT. This aspect also includes challenges related to the monitoring of signal quality to suitably adapt the transmission, compensate the degradation, guarantee optimal performance and/or offer/support services with different QoS level. Especially when MCM and flexi-grid technologies are adopted, the equipment resolution for the parameters acquisition become an issue, due to the wide range of granularities and to the presence of very narrow bandwidth channels. Thus, high-resolution spectral monitoring represents a multi-adaptive transmission enabler in MAN, even further progress is needed for achieving a cost-effective solution, specifically tailored for this network segment.

The use of MCM technology enables rate/distance adaptive transmission and improves the range of granularities, including the subwavelength level. One of the key features offered by the S-BVT is the SDN-enabled spectral

manipulation to aggregate traffic and serving multiple endpoints with a centralized control. Of course, to target the needs of MAN, this must be combined with simplified digital signal processing and low-complex optoelectronic subsystems for an actual cost-effective implementation, as discussed in Sec. 3. Nevertheless, the cost of a centralized more complex transceiver solution can be shared among multiple users, which in turn would be equipped with more simple and cost-effective data plane elements/solutions, for example not sliceable and with basic adaptive functions. By using band multiplexing, a centralized S-BVT with total capacity of 1Tb/s can serve multiple endpoints, requiring a reduced number of optoelectronic blocks (e.g. 17 or 20 BVT modules for 100 endpoints)⁴. From a techno-economic point of view, it has been demonstrated that the proposed S-BVT using MB-OFDM and DD is a viable solution (compared to coherent flexgrid transponders envisioned for core networks) for the application of flexgrid technology in the MAN, covering regional paths up to hundreds of kilometers⁴.

The adoption of a multi-wavelength source or an array of direct modulated lasers can be advantageously introduced to replace the array of TLS, at a cost of limiting the tune-ability range of the S-BVT optical carriers. Additionally, for an actual low cost implementation enabling to exploit the polarization dimension, the polarization controller and beam splitter/combiner elements, and eventually the photodetection stage of each S-BVT module, can be integrated in the same substrate¹⁵.

Actually, the use of photonic technologies and photonic integration can be envisioned in order to meet the metro network requirements in terms of cost, power consumption and footprint, while addressing key issues (e.g. latency) and enabling new advanced features. This together with the efficient exploitation of multiple dimensions, including the spatial one, and the softwarization and intelligent control of data plane allow an optimal usage of the available resources for the design of high capacity and highly scalable next generation optical metro networks.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work has been supported by the Spanish DESTELLO project TEC2015-69256-R.

REFERENCES

- [1] Sambo, N., et al., "Next Generation Sliceable Bandwidth Variable Transponders," *IEEE Comm. Mag.*, 53(2), 163-171 (2015).
- [2] Svaluto Moreolo, M., et. al., "SDN-enabled Sliceable BVT Based on Multicarrier Technology for Multi-Flow Rate/Distance and Grid Adaptation," *IEEE/OSA J. Lightwave Technol.*, 34(6), 1516-1522 (2016).
- [3] Nadal, L., Svaluto Moreolo, M., Fabrega, J. M., and Vilchez, F. J., "Experimental Demonstration of a Programmable S-BVT with PDM Capability for Flexible Optical Metro Networks," *Proc. ECOC*, (2016).
- [4] Svaluto Moreolo, M., Fabrega, J. M., Martín, L., Christodouloupoulos, K., Varvarigos, E., and Fernández-Palacios, J. P., "Flexgrid Technologies Enabling BRAS Centralization in MANs," *J. Opt. Commun. Netw.*, 8(7), A64-A75 (2016).
- [5] Gerstel, O., Jino, M., Lord A., Yoo, S.J. B., "Elastic optical networking: a new dawn for the optical layer?," *IEEE Comm. Mag.*, 50, s12-s20 (2012).
- [6] Casellas, R., et al., "On-Demand Allocation of Control Plane Functions via SDN/NFV for Monitoring-enabled Flexi-grid Optical Networks with Programmable BVTs," *Proc. ECOC*, (2016).
- [7] Fabrega, J.M., Svaluto Moreolo, M., Nadal, L., Vilchez, F. J., Villafranca, A., "Experimental Study of Adaptive Loading in DD OFDM Using In-band Optical Sub-Carrier SNR Monitoring," *Proc. OFC*, Th2A.12 (2016).
- [8] Li, Y., Zhang, Y., and Huang, Y., "Any bias control technique for Mach-Zehnder modulator," *IEEE Photon. Technol. Lett.*, 25 (24), 2412-2415 (2013).
- [9] Muñoz, R., et al., "Dynamic Differential Delay Aware RSA for Elastic Multi-Path Provisioning in GMPLS Flexi-grid DWDM Networks," *Proc. OFC*, W3A.2 (2014).
- [10] Yoshida, Y., et al., "First Demonstration of Cognitive SDN Orchestration: A Real-time Congestion-aware Services Provisioning over OFDM-based 400G OPS and Flexi-WDM OCS Networks," *Proc. OFC*, PDP Th5B.2 (2016).
- [11] Kai, Y., et al., "Experimental Demonstration of a Programmable 400-Gbps DMT Transceiver with Policy-based Control," *Proc. OECC/PS*, (2016).

- [12] Svaluto Moreolo, M., Nadal, L., Fabrega, J. M., "DSP-enabled optical OFDM for multiple-format and multi-rate/distance transmission," Proc. ICTON, We.A1.5 (2015).
- [13] Jansen, S. L., et al., "121.9-Gb/s PDM-OFDM Transmission with 2-b/s/Hz Spectral Efficiency Over 1000 km of SSMF," IEEE/OSA J. Lightwave Technol., 27(3), 177-188 (2009).
- [14] Kottke, C., et al., "154.9 Gb/s OFDM Transmission Using IM-DD, Electrical IQ-Mixing and Signal Combining," Proc. OFC, Th3C.4 (2016).
- [15] Wang, J., et al., "Ultrabroadband Silicon-on-Insulator Polarization Beam Splitter Based on Cascaded Mode-Sorting Asymmetric Y-Junctions," Photon. J., 6(6),1-8 (2014).